

THE MAIN IMPORTANCE OF WRITING SKILLS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: In this article one can find information about the role of writing in the process of learning languages, the several types of writing which are essential in learning period and advantages of writing in foreign language learning.

Key words: learning styles, input and output, formal writing, spelling, keyboard.

In this globalized world everyone tries to become more active and well-known in a language learning. However, most people learn a language with the main goal of speaking it, but rarely consider writing because it does not help hold conversations. However, learning another language apart from their own one makes some difficulties during learning time. The main difficulty is not to write words correctly. It is considered that learner can not develop his/her writing skills enough. The other difficulty in learning another language is pronouncing words and phrases in a pronouncing words and phrases in an incorrectly way; especially learners come across difficulty with busying in English, because of differences between writing and spelling of it.

To solve these problems teachers and tutors teach their student in a very short time with high quality and also students should choose an appropriate way of learning according to their learning styles and learning skills. They may accelerate and simplify some difficulties of foreign language.

There are 3 basic types of learning styles according to Educational psychologist Walter Burke Barbe and his colleagues' theory: they distinguished "modalities of learning"-visual, auditory and kinesthetic.

Relying on this, interviewing scientific surveys and its results show that most of language learners are visual learners type. They can catch easily what they see and many of them prefer to write down what they know and learn. So writing skills allow to visual learners more clarity in knowledge of grammar and consequently, a strong understanding of literary language.

In foreign language, learning taught by two main directions, they are output and input learning. Output language learning is considered speaking and writing which make learners create something by their own. Input language learning is reading and listening that depend on learners attention and thinking carefully. Input and output language learning are closely related; when someone work on

reading, their writing does get better. Also two output skills are related each other: writing and speaking; both require learners to think for yourself and use vocabulary they know to shape their own sentences. Writing however, is like speaking in slow motion, when learners are writing they have more time to think about their words, they may even look up the right way to write things and words they do not know. That's why it can be excellent practice and working with their mind and dictionary, plus, amazing to do written exercises.

In addition all above, there are a few extra reasons why writing is so important in foreign language learning. Writing allows organizing and refining ideas not seeing that it is much slower progress, learners are able to develop their vocabulary source and pronunciations and learn how to spell correctly like native speakers. Also practice and exercises make perfect, even more so in writing. So that over time, they will see the progress of their language learning journey in order to evaluate weak and strong points.

With all words, phrases and rules there are in a language, it may feel hard to memorize them all, but many studies have shown that writing is proven to be helpful in retaining information because putting their learning into practice is important for cementing in their mind, as practice creates new neural pathways in the brain. In addition, learners who have skills to produce academic language in writing, they can easily transfer the argumentative skills to speaking skills, because of relationship between writing and speaking.

Above in this article mentioned that learners have difficulties with realizing phrases and rewrite what they hear or what they want to write. When they write in their new language, learners will likely be missing, some accent and characters. In this situation, recommended to use high ITT-technology like special keyboards to correct inaccurately written words or phrases and make learners work with their omissions. On smart phones, learners should download a keyboard for a new language. The Swiftkey keyboard allows up to five languages at the same time without changing keyboard language as they switch back and forth between them.

Learning foreign languages is today's first task to do. Language is a key every nation Uzbek proverb mentioned (Til – barcha eshiklarning kalitidir). Generally, learning language makes people more creative, active and well-known, social and open-minded.

So using writing in foreign language learning is more important than others. Also it helps taking good results in a short time. As one of the greatest French writers Voltaire said: "Writing is the painting of voice".

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